

1 **Lrrc4 functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 *LRRC4* as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells
10 of the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Wu, M., Huang, C., Gan, K., Huang, H., Chen, Q., Ouyang, J., Tang, Y., Li, X., Yang, Y., Zhou, H.
13 and Zhou, Y., 2006. LRRC4, a putative tumor suppressor gene, requires a functional leucine-rich repeat
14 cassette domain to inhibit proliferation of glioma cells in vitro by modulating the extracellular
15 signal-regulated kinase/protein kinase B/nuclear factor- κ B pathway. *Molecular biology of the cell*, 17(8),
16 pp.3534-3542.